

Synthesis, X-ray diffraction study and biological activity of 8-(4-methyl-2-azothiazolyl)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin

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8-(4-Methyl-2-azothiazolyl)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (HL) has been synthesized and its X-ray diffraction study carried out. Structure of the sample has emerged as tetragonal non-primitive. The compound has been screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Coumarins are highly fluorescent in nature and are used as laser dyes¹. Thiazoles² possess an array of biological activities. Incorporation of thiazole system in coumarin nucleus may impart enhanced biological activity to the resulting compound. In continuation of our earlier work³, synthesis of the title compound (HL) was undertaken in the present investigation.

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Results and Discussion

The purified, dark brown coloured HL gave satisfactory elemental analysis. The assignments of IR bands carried out by a method similar to that suggested by Looker⁴ are in good agreement with the reported values for similar compounds⁵. The main bands observed are 3494 (OH), 1800 (C=O), 1600 (C=C), 1735 (lactone ring), 1454 (-N=N-) and 1274 cm^{-1} (C=N thiazole ring). The electronic spectrum of HL in ethanol displayed mainly four bands at 222, 257, 328 and 480 nm with molar coefficient values of 0.312×10^5 , 0.180×10^5 , 0.289×10^5 and $0.277 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The typical ¹H NMR spectrum of HL shows a doublets at δ 2.38 and 2.40 due to protons of methyl groups present on C₄ position of the coumarin ring and thiazole moiety, respectively. The *ortho*-coupled protons (C₅ and C₆) showed a pair of doublets at δ 7.58, 7.60 and 6.60,

6.62, respectively, which confirms the point of attachment of thiazolyl group at C₈ position. Multiplet signal of aromatic protons appeared in the range δ 7.5 – 8.5.

The sharp and single reflection peaks of the X-ray diffractogram of HL pattern show formation of single phase compound. HL records twenty six reflection between 10° and 80° (2 θ) with maximum intensity peak at 2 θ = 16.350 which corresponds to d = 5.417. The observed d and Q of HL were used to evaluate calculated d and Q . The observed values of d and Q are indexed by using computer software by trial and error method. The indexed method also yielded hkl values.

The tetragonal system was selected for which $\Sigma \Delta d = (d_{\text{obs}} - d_{\text{cal}})$ was minimum, comparison of d values confirms the proper selection of unit cell and crystal system. The experimental density was determined by specific gravity method⁶. From this number of atoms per unit cell were determined. Only integral value ($n = 4$) was considered and theoretical density was calculated⁷, which was in good agreement with the experimental density within the limit of error. The comparison of d and Q on the basis of tetragonal structure gives a unit cell with the lattice constant $a = b = 19.245 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 17.678 \text{ \AA}$ and cell volume $V = 6547 \text{ \AA}^3$. In conjunction with such cell parameters, the conditions such as $a = b \neq c$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$ ⁸ required for the sample to be tetragonal were tested and found to be satisfactory. Hence it may be concluded that the crystal structure of HL is tetragonal. Other parameters such as pore fraction, packing fraction, radius of atom and volume of atom were calculated⁹. Space group and point group were noted from international table of X-ray crystallography¹⁰. All these values are entered in Table 1.

Table 1. X-Ray parameters for 8-(4-methyl-2-azothiazolyl)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin

Structure	Tetragonal
Space group	14/mmm
Laue group	4/m
Point group	4/mmm
Symmetry of lattice	Non primitive
Interfacial angles	$\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$
Lattice parameters	$a = b = 19.245 \text{ \AA}$ $c = 17.678 \text{ \AA}$
Volume of unit cell	6547.40 \AA^3
Radius of atom	6.803 \AA
Volume of atom	1318 \AA^3
Relative density of packing	0.8053
Density of HL (Theor.)	0.306 g/cc
(Exptl.)	0.295 g/cc
Porè fraction	25.718%
Particle size	242.62 Å

A plot of $B\cos\theta$ vs $\sin\theta$ was found to be non-zero slope which indicates absence of strain caused by inhomogeneous lattice distortion or compositional fluctuations. This trend may be attributed to the property of homogeneity of the present sample with respect of particle size. The particle size of HL was found to be 242.62 Å.

Antimicrobial activity of HL was screened against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aerogens*, *Salmonella paratyphi B* and *Proteus vulgaris* and compared with that of the parent compound 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin at a concn. of 100 µg/ml by agar cup-plate method¹¹. For all the species studied, HL was found to be highly active (zone of inhibition 21–27 mm) in comparison to 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (13–16 mm). Antifungal activity study against *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhizopus* also indicates higher activity for HL (18 and 20% inhibition) as compared to the parent coumarin (10 and 12% inhibition, respectively).

Experimental

Elemental analysis was carried out at Microanalytical Laboratory, University of Poona. IR spectrum was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer, NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference and electronic spectrum on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer. The XRD diffractogram was recorded on a Philips PW 3710 diffractometer attached to a digitized computer alongwith graphical assembly in which $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation source connected with the tube Cu-Ni Kv/20 mA was used. All the chemicals used were E. Merck reagents. 4-Methyl-2-aminothiazole and 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin were prepared according to the literature method¹².

Preparation of HL : To a suspension of 4-methyl-2-

aminothiazole (1.14 g, 0.01 mol) in 1 : 1 H_2SO_4 (10 ml) cooled below 5°. was added dropwise a cold (5°) solution of NaNO_2 (0.69 g, 0.01 mol) in water (10 ml). Resultant diazonium salt was coupled with 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1.76 g, 0.01 mol), the solution of which was prepared in 10% NaOH (50 ml), and pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 6 using dil. NaOH. The resulting solid was washed with water and purified using column chromatography.

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References

1. S. Giri, S. S. Rathi, M. K. Machwe and V. V. S. Murti, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1988, **44**, 805; W.-C. Sun, K. R. Gee and R. P. Haugland, *Biomorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 1998, **8**, 3107.
2. D. R. Shridhar, M. V. Jogibhauka, L. C. Joshi, P. P. Narayan, G. Singh, P. P. S. Rao and A. Y. Junnarkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, **23**, 727.
3. P. P. Hankare, A. H. Jagtap, S. S. Chavan and P. S. Battase, *Indian J. Chem.*, (in the press.)
4. H. Looker, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 361.
5. L. S. Jolly and S. Pendse, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 105; A. D. Garde and B. J. Ghiya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 397; K. H. Drexhage in "Topics Applied Physics", ed. F. P. Shafer, Springer, Berlin, 1973, Vol. 1, Chap. 4.
6. K. Jell, R. Waerstad and G. H. McClellan, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.*, 1974, **7**, 404.
7. K. R. Choukimath, R. T. Pattar, V. G. Tulsigiri and B. R. Havinale, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 520.
8. B. D. Cullity, "Elements of X-Ray Diffraction", Addison-Wesley, 1956; H. S. Peiser, H. P. Rooksy and A. J. C. Wilson, "X-Ray Diffraction by Polycrystalline Materials", Institute of Physics, London, 1956.
9. R. T. Pattar, K. R. Choukimath and V. G. Tulsigiri, *Indian J. Phys., Sect. A*, 1999, **73**, 343.
10. J. D. H. Donney and D. Haker, "Tables of Space Group Criteria, Crystallographiques", Naturaliste Canadian, 1940, Vols. 67, 33 and 160.
11. F. Cavanagh, "Analytical Microbiology", Academic, New York, 1963.
12. E. V. O. John and Israelstam, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 240; B. Das and M. K. Raut, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 663.